

INFLUENCE OF INTEREST RATE STRUCTURE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of interest rates on the economic growth of Nigeria between 1981 and 2024. The specific objectives were to assess the effect of the prime lending rate, monetary policy rate, and savings interest rate on real gross domestic product (RGDP). The study employed an ex-post facto research design and used the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method for hypothesis testing, supported by unit root and descriptive analyses. The findings revealed that the prime lending rate had a positive and significant effect on RGDP, the monetary policy rate also showed a positive and significant effect, while the savings interest rate had a positive but non-significant effect on RGDP within the period under review. Based on these results, the study recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria and commercial banks ensure that prime lending rates remain stable and affordable for productive sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and SMEs. It further suggested that monetary authorities use the monetary policy rate proactively to stimulate economic activity, while policies should be designed to strengthen the link between savings and investment through competitive savings rates and financial inclusion strategies. This study contributes to literature by providing updated evidence on the role of interest rate components in Nigeria's economic growth.

Keywords: Interest Rate; Economic Growth; Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP); Monetary Policy Rate; Prime Lending Rate

Introduction

Interest rate plays a central role in economic decision-making by determining the cost of borrowing and the return on savings, thereby influencing investment, credit availability, and resource allocation (Apere&Akarara, 2024; Acha, 2021 cited in Apere&Akarara, 2024). In Nigeria, interest rate behaviour has historically been volatile due to policy shifts, financial crises, and macroeconomic instability, limiting effective investment diversification beyond the oil sector, which accounts for about 90% of GDP (Chuba, 2005 cited in Apere&Akarara, 2024).

Recent data show persistently high borrowing costs: the maximum lending rate reached 29.79% in January 2025, the Monetary Policy Rate remained at 27.50%, the prime lending rate stood at 17.96% in March 2025, and the interbank rate peaked at 28.58%, while savings deposit rates averaged about 7.500% (CBN, 2025; ThisDay, 2025). These high rates constrain access to finance and discourage investment.

The World Bank (2020) attributes high interest rates in Nigeria to weak institutional frameworks and infrastructure, which elevate investment risk. Although reforms such as financial liberalization and interest rate

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adjustments were introduced, they have not significantly stimulated investment growth due to policy inconsistencies. High lending rates, often exceeding 20%, continue to limit private sector investment, despite policy interventions such as the adjustment of the Monetary Policy Rate during periods of inflationary pressure (Toni, 2019).

Empirically, stable and moderate interest rates are essential for sustainable economic growth, while volatility undermines investment and financial intermediation (Abebiyi, 2002 cited in Joseph et al., 2018). At the same time, some studies argue that higher interest rates can enhance investment returns under certain conditions (Darrat& Dickens, 1994 cited in Mutinda, 2024; Mukhtar&Zakaria, 2024). Overall, interest rate dynamics remain a critical determinant of investment behaviour, economic stability, and growth in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Interest rate remains one of the most critical monetary policy instruments for influencing economic growth in any country. In Nigeria, however, persistent fluctuations and misalignments in interest rates have posed significant challenges to sustainable growth. Despite the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) efforts to regulate interest rates through its Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), the economy continues to experience weak growth, rising inflation, and declining investment.

One major problem is that Nigeria's lending rates remain extremely high, often above 20% in commercial banks, making it difficult for businesses, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to access credit for expansion. This has stifled industrial growth, discouraged entrepreneurship, and limited job creation. On the other hand, deposit rates offered to savers are very low and often negative in real terms due to inflation, thereby discouraging savings and reducing capital accumulation in the economy.

Furthermore, high and unstable interest rates have contributed to declining private sector investment, capital flight, and weak foreign direct investment inflows. Nigeria's manufacturing and agricultural sectors, which are critical drivers of economic diversification, have particularly suffered due to high borrowing costs and limited access to affordable credit. The situation has worsened unemployment, increased poverty levels, and reduced the competitiveness of Nigerian products in the global market.

Another pressing issue is that monetary policy adjustments by the CBN aimed at controlling inflation often lead to higher interest rates, which inadvertently slow down economic activities. This has created a policy dilemma where measures to stabilize inflation conflict with the objective of stimulating growth. Consequently, despite various reforms, Nigeria continues to face sluggish GDP growth, widening inequality, and poor living standards.

In summary, the persistent mismatch between interest rate policies and Nigeria's economic realities has created a cycle of weak investment, low productivity, high unemployment, and slow economic growth. This raises the critical question of how interest rate dynamics affect Nigeria's economic growth and what policy direction is most suitable to achieve stability and sustainable development.

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This study aims to explore the effect of interest rates on the economic growth of Nigeria, considering factors such as inflation, investment, consumption, and government expenditure. It seeks to address the gap in understanding how these rates influence both macroeconomic indicators and long-term sustainable growth, with the goal of providing actionable insights for policymakers to enhance economic performance.

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of interest rate on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, to evaluate how the prime lending rate, monetary policy rate, and savings interest rate each influence real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

The study seeks to determine how prime lending rate, monetary policy rate, and savings interest rate affect real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

In order to guide the analysis, the null hypotheses state that prime lending rate, monetary policy rate, and savings interest rate each have no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Interest rate refers to the cost of borrowing money or the return on savings, expressed as a percentage of the principal over a specified period (Teriba, 2022). It represents the payment made by borrowers for the use of funds and the reward to lenders for parting with liquidity. Interest rates may be nominal, where inflation is not considered, or real, where inflation is adjusted. They are typically stated annually as an annual percentage rate (APR) for loans or annual percentage yield (APY) for savings. While low-risk loans attract lower rates, high-risk loans carry higher rates. Savings accounts and similar deposits usually earn compound interest (Caroline, 2025).

The prime lending rate is the benchmark rate charged by commercial banks to their most creditworthy customers and serves as a basis for pricing other loans (James, 2024). It is derived from the federal funds rate, commonly calculated as the policy rate plus about 3%. As of January 2025, the prime rate stood at 7.50%, following an adjustment of the federal funds rate to 4.25%–4.50% in December 2024. Economically, a high prime lending rate discourages borrowing, especially for small and medium enterprises, thereby limiting investment, capital formation, and economic growth (Acha&Acha, 2011). Conversely, a lower prime rate enhances access to credit, stimulates investment and production, and supports economic growth (Nwakanma&Nnamdi, 2013).

The Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) is the benchmark interest rate used by the Central Bank of Nigeria to regulate money supply, control inflation, and influence economic growth. In 2025, Nigeria's MPR stands at 27.50%, representing the cost at which banks borrow from the central bank and shaping lending rates to businesses and individuals (CBN, 2025). Monetary policy operates through tools such as interest rate adjustments, reserve requirements, and open market operations, and may be expansionary or contractionary depending on economic conditions (Caitlin, 2024). Changes in MPR directly affect borrowing costs, investment decisions, and overall economic activity.

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The savings rate is the proportion of disposable income set aside rather than spent, reflecting individuals' or groups' preference for future consumption over present consumption (Julia, 2024). It is calculated as the ratio of personal savings to disposable income and is influenced by economic conditions, institutional factors, and individual behaviour. Savings serve purposes such as investment, retirement, and emergencies, and play a key role in capital formation and economic stability.

Economic growth refers to an increase in the production of goods and services over time, typically measured by real gross domestic product (GDP) or gross national product (GNP) (Charles, 2025). It is driven by factors such as capital accumulation, labour force expansion, technological advancement, and human capital development. Growth leads to higher income levels, improved living standards, and increased consumption. In Nigeria, as in other economies, sustained economic growth depends on efficient resource utilization, investment, and supportive macroeconomic policies.

Theoretical Review

Theories of interest rate explain how rates are determined, with differing views on whether they are driven by monetary or real factors.

The Mundell–Fleming (IS-LM-BP) model, developed in the 1960s by Mundell and Fleming, explains interest rate behaviour in an open economy (Olivier, 2019). It posits that capital flows respond to interest rate differentials: higher domestic rates attract inflows and currency appreciation, while lower rates cause outflows and depreciation (Obstfeld&Rogoff, 1996). Under a fixed exchange rate, a country cannot simultaneously maintain independent monetary policy, making fiscal policy more effective (Mundell, 1963).

The classical theory views interest rate as the equilibrium price that balances savings and investment, determined by the demand and supply of capital. Investment drives demand for funds, while savings determine supply (Gujarati & Porter, 2019).

The Keynesian liquidity preference theory treats interest rate as a monetary phenomenon determined by money demand and supply. It suggests that higher interest rates encourage savings, increase bank lending capacity, and stimulate investment, while low rates may discourage savings (Gujarati & Porter, 2019).

Financial Liberalization Theory was proposed by McKinnon and Shaw (1973), this theory argues that regulated low interest rates 'financial repression' discourage savings and investment, hindering growth. Deregulation, as seen in Nigeria's Structural Adjustment Programme, is expected to raise interest rates, promote savings, improve investment quality, and enhance economic growth.

Much as evidence has shown there are extensive studies exist globally, there is limited long-term evidence in Nigeria linking interest rates, economic growth, and investment decisions, highlighting a gap which this study seeks to address.

Empirical Review

Ologunde et al. (2024) examined the impact of interest rate on investment in Jordan from 1990 to 2022 using co-integration techniques. The findings revealed a strong negative relationship, indicating that a 1 percent

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increase in real interest rate leads to a 44 percent decline in investment, highlighting the sensitivity of investment to borrowing costs.

Olufemi et al. (2023) investigated the relationship between interest rate and real GDP growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1991 to 2021 and the ARDL model. The results showed a significant long-run relationship between interest rate and economic growth, with $\text{Adj } R^2 = 0.44$ and $F\text{-statistic} = 18.55$ ($p < 0.05$), confirming that interest rate plays a critical role in influencing Nigeria's economic performance.

Udoka and Roland (2022) analyzed the effect of interest rate fluctuations on Nigeria's economic growth from 1970 to 2021 using ordinary least squares regression. Their findings indicated an inverse relationship between interest rates and economic growth, suggesting that rising interest rates constrain economic expansion.

Obamuyi and Olorunfemi (2021) explored the relationship between interest rate behavior, financial reform, and economic growth in Nigeria using co-integration and error correction models for the period 1986 to 2020. The study found that interest rates significantly influence economic growth, emphasizing that appropriate interest rate regimes are essential for promoting investment and sustaining economic development.

Gap in Empirical Literature

Although extensive literature exists on the relationship between interest rates and economic growth, notable gaps persist, especially in the Nigerian context. Much of the existing research is concentrated on developed economies with stable financial systems and efficient monetary policy transmission, whereas Nigeria faces distinct structural challenges such as inflation volatility, exchange rate instability, and weak institutional frameworks that are insufficiently addressed.

In addition, many Nigerian studies treat interest rate as a single static variable, with limited attention to its dynamic nature, including variations between short-term and long-term rates and the effects of interest rate volatility. There is also inadequate sector-specific analysis, particularly regarding how interest rates differently impact key sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, and the informal economy.

Moreover, recent economic developments, including the COVID-19 pandemic, fluctuations in global oil prices, and ongoing monetary policy reforms by the Central Bank of Nigeria, have not been fully incorporated into existing studies.

Consequently, the gap lies in the lack of a comprehensive, up-to-date analysis that captures the dynamic, sectoral, and evolving nature of interest rates and their effects on Nigeria's economic growth. This study addresses this gap by utilizing recent data and examining both direct and indirect impacts across major sectors of the economy.

Methodology**Model Specification**

A model is a simplified view of reality designed to enable a researcher describe the essence and inter relationship within the system or phenomenon it depicts (Onwumere, 2005). The hypotheses will be tested

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using the Simple Linear Regression Model. In writing the model equation, the following symbols were used to denote their respective variables.

$$RGDP = f(PLR, MPR, SIR, INFR) \dots \dots \dots 3.0$$

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PLR_t + \beta_2 MPR_t + \beta_3 SIR_t + \beta_4 INFR_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

Where:

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate

PLR = Prime Lending rate

MPR = Monetary Policy Rate

SIR = Savings Interest Rate

INFR = Inflation Rate (Control Variable)

β_0 = Constant of the equation

β = Coefficient of the independent variable

μ = Error terms

Hypothesis one

Thus, for hypothesis one which states that Prime Lending rate has no positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria.

It was represented by the equation.

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PLR_t + \beta_2 INFR_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3.2$$

Hypothesis two

For hypothesis two, which states that Monetary Policy Rate has no positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria, it was represented by the equation

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_t + \beta_2 INFR_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3.3$$

Hypothesis three

For hypothesis three, which states that Savings Interest rate has no positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria, it was represented by the equation

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SIR_t + \beta_2 INFR_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3.4$$

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopted Ordinary Least Square method for hypotheses testing. Other preliminary analysis such as unit root test and descriptive Analyses was employed to thoroughly examine the data.

Economic a priori expectation

The test is aimed at determining whether the signs and sizes of the results are in line with what economic theory postulates. Thus, economic theory tells us that the coefficients are positively related to the dependent variable, if an increase in any of the explanatory variables leads to a decrease in the dependent variable.

Therefore, the variable under consideration and their parameter exhibition of a priori signs have been summarized in the table below.

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This table will be guarded by these criteria

When $\beta > 0$ = conform.

When $\beta < 0$ = not conform.

Table 3.1: Economic a priori expectation

Variables	Expected sign	Conclusion
RGDP	+	Conforms
PLR	-	Does not Conforms
MPR	-	Does not Conforms
SIR	+	Conforms
INFR	-	Does not Conforms

From the above table, it is observed that the signs of RGDP, PLR, MPR, INFR parameters is expected to have a negative sign while SIR is expected to conform.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

	RGDP01	PLR01	MPR01	SIR01	INFR01
Mean	0.000778	1.337578	1.015839	0.486605	0.136539
Median	0.000381	1.307427	1.000000	0.322205	0.112437
Maximum	0.003579	3.464674	2.719033	2.554348	0.583090
Minimum	0.000120	0.277046	0.185338	0.099705	0.003803
Std. Dev.	0.000960	0.782915	0.578861	0.473223	0.137251
Skewness	1.818517	0.871043	0.882934	2.569990	1.578939
Kurtosis	4.947408	3.566489	3.871078	10.32948	5.148140
Jarque-Bera	30.49490	6.012433	6.946404	143.5854	26.13451
Probability	0.000000	0.049479	0.031018	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	0.033453	57.51585	43.68107	20.92401	5.871194
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.87E-05	25.74412	14.07337	9.405473	0.791186
Observations	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Eviews, output, 9.0

The normality test adopted in table 4.1 above is the Jarque-Bera (JB) test of normality. The JB test of normality is a large sample test and is based on the OLS residuals. The test computes the skewness and kurtosis measures of the OLS residuals. From the above analysis all the probability of Jarque-Bera statistic is greater than 5% i.

Research Article

0.000000(LRGDP), 0.049479(PLR), 0.031018(MPR), 0.000000(SIR), 0.000002(INFR) less than 0.05, therefore we conclude that all the variables are normally distributed.

Unit Root Test

For a guide to an appropriate specification of the regression equation, the characteristics of the time series data used for estimation of the model were examined to avoid spurious regression. We begin by determining the underlying properties of the process that generate out time series variables that is whether the variables in our model were stationary or non-stationary using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF):

Table 4.2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Result

Variables	ADF - statistic	Critical values 1%	Critical values 5%	Critical values 10%	Prob.	Order of Integration
D(LRGDP)	-5.493116	-3.592462	-2.931404	-2.603944	0.0000	1(0)
D(PLR)	-5.886003	-3.592462	-2.931404	-2.603944	0.0000	1(0)
D(MPR)	-5.634140	-3.592462	-2.931404	-2.603944	0.0000	1(0)
D(SIR)	-4.273326	-3.592462	-2.931404	-2.603944	0.0015	1(0)
INFR	-5.785435	-3.596616	-2.933158	-2.604867	0.0000	1(0)

Source: Researcher's Computation using E-view, 9.0

The result above in table 4.2 shows that Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) is stationary with the result of ADF Test Statistics of -5.493116 which is greater than Critical Value of -2.931404 with p-value 0.0000 less than 0.05%.

Prime Lending rate, is stationary with the result of ADF Test Statistics of -5.886003 which is greater than Critical Value of -2.931404 with p-value 0.0000 less than 0.05%.

Monetary Policy Rate is stationary with the result of ADF Test Statistics of -5.634140 which is greater than Critical Value of -2.931404 with p-value 0.0000 less than 0.05%.

Savings Interest Rate is stationary with the result of ADF Test Statistics of -4.273326 which is greater than Critical Value of -2.931404 with p-value 0.0015 less than 0.05%.

Inflation Rate is stationary with the result of ADF Test Statistics of -5.785435 which is greater than Critical Value of -2.933158 with p-value 0.0000 less than 0.05%.

The result above in table 4.2 shows that all variables are stationary at level (1(0)). This is deducted from the fact that at levels of variables, the all the absolute values of the ADF statistics are greater than the critical values of the ADF at 5% level of significance. Showing that all the variables are stationary.

Johansen Co-Integration Test

The co-integration analysis helps to test for the existence of long run stable relationship that exists between the dependent variable and its regression. Following the approach of Johansen and Juselius (1990) two likelihood

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ratio test statistic, the maximal eigen value and the trace statistic were utilized to determine the number of co-integration vectors.

Table 4.3: Johansen Co-Integration Test

Date: 07/01/25 Time: 17:30

Sample (adjusted): 1983 2024

Included observations: 42 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: RGDP1 PLR1 MPR1 SIR1 INFR1

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.758684	134.1007	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.599440	74.39160	47.85613	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.350906	35.96616	29.79707	0.0086
At most 3 *	0.212799	17.81468	15.49471	0.0220
At most 4 *	0.168802	7.765243	3.841466	0.0053

Trace test indicates 5 cointegratingeqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.758684	59.70913	33.87687	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.599440	38.42544	27.58434	0.0014
At most 2	0.350906	18.15149	21.13162	0.1243
At most 3	0.212799	10.04943	14.26460	0.2087
At most 4 *	0.168802	7.765243	3.841466	0.0053

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegratingeqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

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**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Eviews, output, 9.0

From table 4.3 above the trace statistic of 134.1007 clearly exceed the critical values of 69.81889 with probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$ percent confidence interval, hence, we are not accepting the null hypothesis and conclude that there is cointegrating relationship and therefore, a long run equilibrium relationship exists among the variables.

TEST OF RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Hypotheses One:

H₁: Prime Lending rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria

Table 4.4 Ordinary Least Square Model

Dependent Variable: RGDP1

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/01/25 Time: 17:33

Sample: 1981 2024

Included observations: 44

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.000257	1224.916	0.000210	1.0000
PLR1	1208.240	407.6851	2.963661	0.0050
INFR1	85.02146	100.6121	0.845042	0.4030
R-squared	0.215948	Mean dependent var		-1.39E-10
Adjusted R-squared	0.177701	S.D. dependent var		8960.204
S.E. of regression	8125.174	Akaike info criterion		20.90907
Sum squared resid	2.71E+09	Schwarz criterion		21.03072
Log likelihood	-456.9995	Hannan-Quinn criter.		20.95418
F-statistic	5.646216	Durbin-Watson stat		1.547882
Prob(F-statistic)	0.006825			

Source: Eviews, output, 9.0

Based on table 4.4, the interpretation of the results as regard the coefficient of various repressors' is stated as follows:

The value of the intercept which is 0.000257 shows that the Nigerian Real Gross Domestic Product will experience 0.000257% increase when all other variables are held constant.

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The estimate coefficients which are 1208.240(PLR) shows that a unit change in Prime Lending rate will cause 1208.240% increase in Real Gross Domestic Product

From the analysis R^2 is 0.215948 showing that 22% variation in Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variable Prime lending rate (PLR).

F-Statistics shows that Prime Lending rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria with F- statistics (5.646216; p-value = 0.006825 > 0.05).

Table 4.5 above also indicates that Prime Lending rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria with t- statistics (2.963661; p-value = 0.0050 < 0.05).

Hypotheses Two:

H₂: Monetary Policy Rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria

Table 4.5 Ordinary Least Square Model

Dependent Variable: RGDP1

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/01/25 Time: 17:34

Sample: 1981 2024

Included observations: 44

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.000473	1078.378	-0.000439	1.0000
MPR1	1659.013	344.1931	4.820006	0.0000
INFR1	66.71597	88.03046	0.757874	0.4529
R-squared	0.392321	Mean dependent var		-1.39E-10
Adjusted R-squared	0.362678	S.D. dependent var		8960.204
S.E. of regression	7153.148	Akaike info criterion		20.65424
Sum squared resid	2.10E+09	Schwarz criterion		20.77589
Log likelihood	-451.3933	Hannan-Quinn criter.		20.69935
F-statistic	13.23493	Durbin-Watson stat		1.492855
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000037			

Source: Eviews, output, 9.0

Based on table 4.5, the interpretation of the results as regard the coefficient of various repressors' is stated as follows:

The value of the intercept which is -0.000473 shows that the Nigerian Real Gross Domestic Product will experience -0.000473% decrease when all other variables are held constant.

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The estimate coefficients which are 1659.013(MPRR) shows that a unit change in Monetary Policy rate will cause 1659.013% increase in Real Gross Domestic Product

From the analysis R^2 is 0.392321 showing that 39% variation in Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variable Monetary Policy Rate (MPR).

F-Statistics shows that Monetary Policy Rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria with F- statistics (13.23493; p-value = 0.000037 > 0.05).

Table 4.5 above also indicates that Monetary Policy Rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria with t- statistics (4.820006; p-value = 0.0000 < 0.05).

Hypotheses Three:

H₃: Savings Interest rate has positive and significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria

Table 4.6 Ordinary Least Square Model

Dependent Variable: RGDP1

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/01/25 Time: 17:36

Sample (adjusted): 1982 2024

Included observations: 43 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.001144	0.000198	5.773720	0.0000
SIR1	0.000404	0.000344	1.172935	0.2478
INFR1	-0.004120	0.001187	-3.469213	0.0013
R-squared	0.248167	Mean dependent var		0.000778
Adjusted R-squared	0.210575	S.D. dependent var		0.000960
S.E. of regression	0.000853	Akaike info criterion		-11.22829
Sum squared resid	2.91E-05	Schwarz criterion		-11.10542
Log likelihood	244.4082	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-11.18298
F-statistic	6.601642	Durbin-Watson stat		0.841276
Prob(F-statistic)	0.003330			

Source: Eviews, output, 9.0

Based on table 4.6, the interpretation of the results as regard the coefficient of various repressors' is stated as follows:

The value of the intercept which is 0.001144 shows that the Nigerian Real Gross Domestic Product will experience 0.001144% increase when all other variables are held constant.

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The estimate coefficients which are 0.000404(SIR) shows that a unit change in Savings Interest Rate will cause 0.00404% increase in Real Gross Domestic Product

From the analysis R^2 is 0.248167 showing that 25% variation in Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) can be explained by the independent variable Savings Interest Rate(SIR).

F-Statistics shows that Savings Interest rate has positive and non-significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeriawith F-statistics (6.601642; p-value = 0.003330 < 0.05).

Table 4.6 above also indicates that Savings Interest rate has positive and non-significant effect on Real Gross domestic product in Nigeria within the period under review with t- statistics (1.172935; p-value = 0.2478 > 0.05).

Discussion of Findings

The value of the intercept which is 0.000257 implies that Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) would increase by 0.000257% when other factors are held constant. The coefficient of Prime Lending Rate (PLR) at 1208.240 indicates that a unit increase in PLR leads to a 1208.240% rise in RGDP. The model explains about 22% of the variation in RGDP ($R^2 = 0.215948$). Both the F-statistic (5.646216; p-value = 0.006825) and t-statistic (2.963661; p-value = 0.0050 < 0.05) confirm that PLR has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 4.5 above for the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) with the intercept of -0.000473 suggests a slight decrease of 0.000473% in RGDP when other variables are constant. The coefficient of 1659.013 shows that a unit increase in MPR increases RGDP by 1659.013%. The explanatory power is stronger, with $R^2 = 0.392321$, indicating that about 39% of RGDP variation is explained. The F-statistic (13.23493; p-value = 0.000037) and t-statistic (4.820006; p-value = 0.0000 < 0.05) reveal that MPR has a positive and statistically significant effect on RGDP.

F-Statistics shows that Savings Interest Rate (SIR) with the intercept of 0.001144 indicates a 0.001144% increase in RGDP when other variables are constant. The coefficient of 0.000404 shows that a unit increase in SIR results in a 0.00404% rise in RGDP. The model explains about 25% of RGDP variation ($R^2 = 0.248167$). While the F-statistic (6.601642; p-value = 0.003330 < 0.05) suggests overall model significance, the t-statistic (1.172935; p-value = 0.2478 > 0.05) indicates that SIR has a positive but statistically non-significant effect on economic growth within the study period.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary of Findings

The study examined the effect of interest rates on Nigeria's economic growth using annual data from 1981 to 2024. The results show that the Prime Lending Rate has a positive and statistically significant effect on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), with t-statistic of 2.963661 and p-value of 0.0050 < 0.05. Similarly, the Monetary Policy Rate also exerts a positive and significant impact on RGDP, with F-statistic of 13.23493 and

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p-value of 0.000037. In contrast, the Savings Interest Rate shows a positive but statistically non-significant effect on RGDP, with t-statistic of 1.172935 and p-value of $0.2478 > 0.05$.

Conclusion

The study concludes that interest rate variables influence Nigeria's economic growth, though their impacts differ. Prime Lending Rate and Monetary Policy Rate both have positive and significant effects on RGDP, indicating their importance in driving economic productivity and reflecting the effectiveness of monetary policy actions. However, Savings Interest Rate, despite its positive relationship, does not significantly influence economic growth within the study period. Overall, the findings suggest that policy focus should prioritize effective management of lending and monetary policy rates, as they play a more critical role in stimulating investment and economic expansion than savings rates.

References

- Adegoke, T. D., Azeez, B. A., Ogiemien, F. O., & Osasona, V. A., (2021). The Relationship between Interest Rate and Economic Growth in Nigeria: ARDL Approach. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* |Volume V, Issue VII, Page 350.
- Adekunla, I. A. and Akungba, C. K., (2019). "Interest Rates in Nigeria: An Analytical Perspective "
- Agenor, P. & Montiel, P. (2019). *Development Macroeconomics*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Ahuja, A., (2013). Uncovered Interest Parity and Financial Market Volatility. *The Romanian Economic Journal* (2) (32) 21- 45.
- Aiyedogbon, J. O. C., (2021). Military expenditure and gross capital formation in Nigeria. 1980 – 2023. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. 7(1), 290-310.
- Akani, H. W., and Obiosa, A. L., (2020). Financial sector development and macroeconomic stability in Nigeria: A long –run analysis. *International Journal of Empirical Finance*, 5 (2), 112 – 128.
- Akujuobi, A.B.C., (2020). Foreign direct investments and capital formation in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in National Development*; 5 (2), 13 – 26.
- Alasha, O.A. ((2021). Interest Rate Policy, Savings and Investment in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 31(3) pp. 34-52.

Research Article

- Caitlin, C (2024). Monetary Policy Meaning, Types, and Tools.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/monetarpolicy.asp>
- Caroline, B (2025). Interest Rates: Types and What They Mean to Borrowers.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/interestrates.asp>
- CBN (2025). Key Decisions of the Central Bank of Nigeria Monetary Policy Committee February 19-20, 2025.
<https://www.cbn.gov.ng/MonetaryPolicy/decisions.html#:~:text=The%20Committee%20decided%20at%20the,500/%2D100%20basis%20points.>
- Charles, P. (2025). Economic Growth: What It Is and How It Is Measured.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/e/economicgrowth.asp>
- Chizea, B. (2020) Interest Rates, Exchange Rates and Inflation. *The Nigerian Banker Oct-Dec. 6-11.*
- Chris, M. & Anyingang, D. (2017). Foreign Debt Instability: An Analysis of National Savings and Domestic Investment Response to Foreign Debt Accumulation in 28 Developing Countries. *J. Int. Money Finance.*
- De Gregorio, B. J., and Guidotti, A.O., (2019). Effect of Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Social & Management Sciences* | ISSN: 2488-9849, Vol. 4, Issue 1.
- Donwa, A., and Odiya, U. (2019). the relationship between interest rate and stock price: Empirical evidence from developed and developing countries. *International journal of business and management*, Vol.4, No 3, pp. 43-51.
- Ezekwesili, K.A., (2022). Domestic investment, capital formation and population growth in Nigeria. *Developing Country Studies*, 2(7), 28 – 39.
- Fatoumata K. M., (2017). Impact of Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Pyrex Journal of Business and Finance Management Research* Vol 3 (3) pp. 98-111.
- Gujarati, G. & Porter, R. (2019). The Return of Interest Rate Caps. *Business World Publication*, May.

Research Article

- Hasanov, A. A., (2023). Interest Rate and Economic Growth: The Case of Nigeria. *International Review of Business Research Paper*. Pp. 141-150.
- Hsing, S.I., (2023). Capital Expenditures and Gross Fixed Capital Formation in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable development*, the International Institute for Science, Technology and Education (IISTE).
- James, C. (2024). Prime Rate: Definition and How It Works. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/primerate.asp>
- Jhingan, O.A. (1997). Interest Rate Policy, Savings and Investment in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 31(3) pp. 34-52.
- Julia, K. (2024). What Are Savings? How to Calculate Your Savings Rate. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/savings.asp>
- Kanu, S. I., & Ozurumba, B. A., (2024). Capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria, *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Economics*, 14 (4), 36-55.
- Obamuyi, A.E. and Olorunfemi, A.K., (2021). Impact of capital formation on the growth of Nigerian economy 1960-2023: vector error correction model (vecm). *School of Business Studies, Readings in Management and Social Studies*, 1(1), 132 - 154.
- Obamuyi, T.M. (2019). Financial reforms, interest rate behaviour and Economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Finance and Banking*, vol 1, no 4, page 39-55.
- Olaniyan, N. O., Adegboyo, O. S., Olumuyiwa, O. B., & Abidemi, A. A. (2020). Interest Rate and Economic Growth as Determinants of Firm's Investment Decision in Nigeria: A Cointegration Approach: Array. *Euro Economica*, 39(3). Retrieved from <https://dj.univdanubius.ro/index.php/EE/article/view/748>.
- Olivier, P.B. (2019). Interest Rate Variation and Investment Determination in Nigeria. *International Business Management*, 4 (2), pp. 41-46.
- Ologunde, E., & Nwezeaku, N. C. (2024). The Impact of public sector financial management on the economies of Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics Issue 40 (8)*, 20 - 31

Research Article

- Olubanjo, A., Atobatele, P. and Akinwumi, N. (2023). foreign private investment, capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria: a two stage least square approach. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*.
- Olubanjo, D., Mahmudul, A., & Gazi Salah, U. (2023). The relationship between interest rate and stock price: Empirical evidence from developed and developing countries. *International journal of business and management*, Vol.4, No 3, pp. 43-51.
- Omoke, P. and Oruta, B. (2020). Interest Rate Variation and Investment Determination in Nigeria. *International Business Management*, 4 (2), pp. 41-46.
- Richard, I. M., (2018). Capital formation: Impact on the economic development of Nigeria 1960 – 2013. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*, 3 (3), 1 – 16.
- Samuel, G.; Torbira, L.L., & Ogbulu, O.M., (2017). Fund mobilization by insurance companies and fixed capital formation: Evidence from the Nigerian Economy. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 5(2), 69-81.
- Shuaib, R., Ekeria, G. and Ogedengbe, R. (2024). Empirical investigation of impact of capital formation by agriculture and industry on industrial productivity in india. *Research Journal of Management Sciences*, 2(3), 8-11.
- Udoka, S. and Roland, U., (2022). The impact of capital formation on the growth of Nigerian economy. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(9), 36-40
- Uremadu, R., (2020). Linkages between export, import and capital formation in India. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 16-19.
- Utile, N.F (2018). Two to Tangle: Finance, Instability and Economic Growth in Argentina since 1890, with Karanasos M and Tan B. *Journal of Banking and Finance* 36(1):290-304.
- Zhang, P and Bing, L.B (2020). Interest Rate and Economic Growth: Are they related? Centre for Retirement Research at Boston College Working Papers WP#2024-8, Cambridge, MA. https://crr.bc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/wp_2024-8.pdf

Research Article

- Apere, T.O &Akarara, E.A (2024).Interest Rate and Investment Nexus in Nigeria.International Journal of Advanced Studies in Business Strategies and Management | IJASBSM. 11(1), 260-270
- Acha, I. A. &Acha, C. K. (2021). Interest rates in Nigeria: An analytical perspective, Research Journal of Finance and Accounting. ISSN 2222. 2 (3) 71-82
- Chuba, M. A. (2005). Interest rates policy and investment behaviour in Nigeria, Journal of Economics and Social Research. 3(2)
- Toni O. (2019). Rationale and solutions to high interest rates in Nigeria. www.thecable.ng
- Abebiyi,C. (2002). Interest rate reforms and economic growth: the savings and investment channel. MPRA Paper 85297, University Library of Munich, Germany. https://mpra.ub.unimuenchen.de/85297/1/MPRA_paper_85297.pdf
- Joseph BU, Ogwa AO, Dooter MI (2018). Effects of Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria. International Journal of Advanced Academic Research / Social and Management Sciences 4(1):66-76
- Haron, G. (2023). The Impact of Interest Rate on Economic Growth Example of Nigeria. African Journal of Social Sciences 6(2):51-64.
- Darrat, P and Dickens, B. (199). Interest Rate and Economic Growth: Are they related? Centre for Retirement Research at Boston College Working Papers WP#2024-8, Cambridge, MA. https://crr.bc.edu/wpcontent/uploads/2024/05/wp_2024-8.pdf
- Mutinda DM (2024). The Effect of Lending Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Kenya Master's thesis, University of Nairobi Nairobi, Kenya). Retrieved from <https://chss.uonbi.ac.ke/sites/default/files/chss/Musyoka%20Dan%20Project-2-1%20pdf.pdf>.
- Mukhtar T, Zakaria M (2024). Budget Deficits and Interest Rates: An Empirical Analysis for Pakistan. Journal of Economic Cooperation 29(2):1-14
- CBN (2025). Key Decisions of the Central Bank of Nigeria Monetary Policy Committee February 19-20, 2025. <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/MonetaryPolicy/decisions.html#:~:text=The%20Committee%20decided%20at%20the,500/%2D100%20basis%20points.>